

Enhanced Fault Detection in Transmission Lines Using Variational Mode Decomposition

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Abstract: Rapid detection and repair of transmission line faults are crucial for ensuring the reliable operation of power systems. This study proposes an effective method for identifying and diagnosing such faults using Variational Mode Decomposition (VMD) to analyze fault transients. The initial Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs) are extracted through VMD, which decomposes transmission line voltage signals into a finite number of IMFs, each representing specific frequency components. Unlike traditional methods, VMD offers a more refined time-frequency analysis. A fault index is generated by analyzing the instantaneous energy of the IMFs, allowing for the accurate detection of different types of transmission line faults. The proposed method is validated through simulations, showing robust performance in fault detection thus offering a reliable tool for enhancing power system resilience.

Keywords- Transmission lines, Distance relays, Fault Detection, VMD.

I. INTRODUCTION

The transmission network is complex, with many lines, limited power supply coverage, and a mix of overhead lines and cables. As a result, pinpointing the exact location of faults within the network is particularly challenging; nevertheless, accurate fault detection is essential in transmission networks because it decreases outage durations, minimizes expenses linked to replacing fault lines, and improves overall system reliability.

The necessity for choice, rapid operation, and dependable operation, as well as the safety of electrical equipment, play significant roles in power systems. The procedure should begin with fault detection, which has to be done more precisely and swiftly. It is the goal of power generation facilities and distribution networks to ensure that consumers never lose power. That is why it is crucial to provide them with the right protection strategy quickly. There is no way to adequately safeguard a transmission line without fault detection and faulted-phase selection. Over the years, several defect detection algorithms have been suggested to enhance their protection schemes' capabilities. Here are a few ways that faults can be detected and classified: A strategy based on current slope was suggested in [1]. This method takes current signals as the fault index and uses them to estimate the total of the slopes over data cycles. This study [2] delves into a variety of signal processing methods, comprising an impedance-based measuring approach [3], a wavelet-based method [4], an AI-based

(artificial intelligence) method[5], a method based on the travelling wave phenomena[6], and a few specialised techniques for detecting transmission network defects. Both the immediate and long-term accuracy of the procedures are diminished.

In [7], a method is presented for detecting and classifying various shunt faults. In order to avoid the inherent mistake caused by CT, this work exclusively discusses shunt faults and [8] outlines a method for fault-location on transmission lines that relies solely on synchronised voltage measurements at both ends of the line. The effect of fault resistance is negligible. The greatest magnitude of the superimposed components of the predicted voltage at tee-point before and after the fault are compared in [9]. When it comes to finding high resistance, flaws close to the tee-point, it has its limitations.

This work presents the development of a defect detection approach that is based on Variational Mode Decomposition (VMD). The three-phase instantaneous signals of the terminal voltages and/or currents converted into modal values at the same instant. Afterwards, the signal is subjected to VMD to isolate the high-frequency components as IMFs. Lastly, a threshold value is defined to differentiate between fault and non-fault occurrences, and an energy index is built using these extracted IMFs. We test a two-terminal circuit robustness by simulating a range of failure scenarios with varying values for parameters like resistance, distance, and initiation time. The outcomes demonstrate that the suggested approach may maintain responsiveness, efficiency, and dependability.

This paper's contribution is laid out as follows: The literature summary describes Section-I provides a brief introduction to the subject, while Section-II explores the algorithms that have been suggested. Two terminal algorithms have been recommended in Section III. Following this, portion IV presents the simulation's findings, and Section V is the conclusive portion.

II. Examining the Two-Terminal Line Structure for Analytical

We take into account the two-terminal network presented in Fig.1. A transmission system operating at 345 kV and 50 Hz is used to assess the concept. The linear parameters are resistance $R_0 = 0.01577 \Omega/\text{km}$ and $R_1 = 0.0188 \Omega/\text{km}$... $L_0 = 2.4 \text{ mH}/\text{km}$ and $L_1 = 0.85 \text{ mH}/\text{km}$ are the inductance values. The starting capacitance is $0.0078 \mu\text{F}/\text{km}$ and the starting capacitance is $0.015 \mu\text{F}/\text{km}$. We settle on 1 kHz as our sampling frequency. The simulations were conducted using the MATLAB program. In power system engineering, understanding the network's behaviour under various operating situations is crucial, and one way to do this is through study of two-terminal networks. The suggested method's response test and simulation analysis are carried out using the single line circuit for teed circuit illustrated in Fig. 1. On the MATLAB/SIMULINK 2020 platform, the system is simulated.

Fig.1. A single-line representation of a two-terminal transmission network

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY FOR FAULT DETECTION

A. Variational Mode Decomposition (VMD)

Decomposing a real-valued input signal c into several discrete modal signals y_n with sparse qualities is the goal of VMD, a non-recursive modal variational approach first proposed by Dragomiretskiy et al. [10] for use in signal processing. Based on a predefined decomposition scale n , VMD can automatically and effectively separate the frequency domain and complex signal components by searching for the maximum and minimum iteratively. This technique tackles the problem of differentiating near-frequency components and successfully removes aliasing between the decomposed signals. This model of constraint variation is shown below.

$$\min_{\{y_n\}, \{m_n\}} \left\{ \sum_n \left\| \partial_t \left[\left(\delta(t) + \frac{j}{\pi t} \right) * y_n(t) \right] e^{-jm_n t} \right\|_2^2 \right\} \text{ s.t. } \sum_n y_n = c \quad (1)$$

where, $\{y_n\} = \{y_1, \dots, y_N\}$ and $\{m_n\} = \{m_1, \dots, m_N\}$ collection of various modes and their centre frequencies correspondingly.

To get the enhanced Lagrangian formulation, a second penalty component α and the Lagrangian multiplication operator $\lambda(t)$ are utilised. The saddle point of the augmented Lagrangian function is then solved using an alternate direction method of multipliers (ADMM) iterative technique, yielding the best solution for restricted variational expressions. Using Parseval/Plancherel and Fourier transform, the best representation of modal component and centre frequency is stated as

$$\hat{u}_n(\omega) = \frac{\hat{x}(\omega) - \sum_{i \neq n} \hat{u}_i(\omega) + \frac{\hat{\lambda}(\omega)}{2}}{1 + 2\alpha(\omega - \omega_n)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\omega_n = \frac{\int_0^\infty \omega |\hat{u}_n(\omega)|^2 d\omega}{\int_0^\infty |\hat{u}_n(\omega)|^2 d\omega} \quad (3)$$

where, $\hat{x}(\omega)$, $\hat{u}_i(\omega)$, $\hat{\lambda}(\omega)$ and $\hat{u}_n(\omega)$ are the Fourier transforms of $x(t)$, $u_i(t)$, $\lambda(t)$ and $u_n(t)$, respectively.

A number of intrinsic mode function (IMF) signals are extracted from the initial mode signal and evaluated by employing the Variational Mode Decomposition (VMD) method [11], [12], and [13]. When working with a time-domain signal x , the VMD approach can be helpful for splitting it into many independent multi-frequency (IMF) signals of varying time scales. This is achieved by shifting the signal within each IMF. In order to separate the various components of signal x , the decomposition method is analogous to wavelet decomposition in that it builds sub-bands according to the need. The signal's highest frequency portion is contained in the first IMF, which is called IMF1. The subsequent levels may be broken down in the same way, with the residual mode serving as the final mode. The residual mode is the last mode after decomposing the following layers. VMD is data-driven and filter-free. At least one minimal and one maximal are needed to decompose any signal x into IMFs.

The process for executing the VMD method is as follows.

Section One: Establish the preliminary value of $\{\hat{u}_n^1\}$, $\{\omega_n^1\}$, $\hat{\lambda}^1$ and k to zero. n denotes the decomposed times, which must be a positive integer, $k = k + 1$.

Section One: Based on (2) and (3), u_n and ω_n is updated respectively, until n times.

Section One: $\hat{\lambda}$ is updated via $\hat{\lambda}^{k+1}(\omega) \leftarrow \hat{\lambda}^k(\omega) + \tau[\hat{x}(\omega) - \sum_n \hat{u}_n^{k+1}(\omega)]$, this can be adjusted to zero when the fidelity requirements for the decomposition results are minimal, and where τ is the modify parameter.

Section One: Repeat 2 to 3, when $\sum_n \frac{\|\hat{u}_n^{k+1} - \hat{u}_n^k\|_2^2}{\|\hat{u}_n^k\|_2^2} < \epsilon$, the loop is terminated, and the output is provided.

B. Scheme for Detecting Faults

Step:1 Choosing the activating signal as the three-phase instantaneous modal voltages for the logic of the relays

Step:2 Variational Mode Decomposition (VMD)

Step:3 One non-stationary signal 'N_t' may be broken down into two parts using the VMD: the baseline (K_t) and the residual (S_t).

$$N_t = \zeta N_t + (1-\zeta) N_t = K_t + S_t \tag{3}$$

Step:4 Kurtosis statistic:

$$\gamma = E (K_t - \mu)^4 \div (\sigma)^4 \tag{4}$$

Step:5 Index of Energy

$$E_K = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |K_i(n)|^2 \tag{5}$$

Step:6 Set threshold

$$E_{th}$$

Step:7 Fault is detected if

$$E_B > E_{th}$$

FLOW CHART:

Fig.2. A Flow chart representation illustrating the proposed methodology.

IV. THE OUTCOME AND ANALYSIS OF THE SIMULATION

We put the test system through its paces by simulating all kinds of errors. For two cycles, the voltage signals are recorded at both ends of the transmission line for 0.1 s (for 5 cycles). By converting the phase voltage signal to modal values of decomposition, its VMD may be derived. Determined are the intrinsic mode functions at the decomposition level. Following the steps outlined below, multiply the intrinsic mode functions by 1. According to the research plan, this is called a defect index. Determine the maximum values of the fault indices and categorize the different fault kinds using the VMD.

A. Detection results.

This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of finding faults on two-terminal lines in restoring these lines to the network after a fault has occurred using data collected after the fact. This data is retrieved once the fault detection procedure is finished. So, to show how effective the VMD based method is, the article employs it to find problems fast.

i. Line to Ground Fault.

Line-to-ground (LG) faults are simulated at 20% of line length with an inception angle of 120° degrees and fault resistance of 50ohms. VMD is used to deconstruct the output modal value from bus-S voltages. The first level of breakdown yields IMFs. The suggested fault index is derived using IMFs at the first decomposition level. In sequence, Fig. 3 (a), (b), and (c) show bus-S three-phase voltages, modal values, and IMF at the first level of decomposition.

Fig.3. Configuration settings on bus-S at 20% of line length during LG failure (a) three phase voltages (b) Modal voltage Signal (c) intrinsic mode function-1

As seen in Fig. 3 (c), the fault index was computed on bus-S during the creation event at 0.02666 seconds LG fault, which is at the close-end. We find that the fault index is initially set to zero before any faults occur. As a

result, the suggested technique successfully detects LG faults in 0.02691 seconds. Therefore, the issue was identified within 0.25 milliseconds of the fault occurring.

ii. Double Line Fault.

The voltages recorded on line are decomposed to give the modal value of the output, which is further decomposed using VMD. IMFs are acquired at the first decomposition level after simulating a double line (LL) fault at 40% of the line length, 180° inception angle, and 100Ω fault resistance. At the first level of decomposition, IMFs are used to derive the proposed fault index. Fig. 4 (a), (b), and (c) show the three phase voltages, modal values, and IMF at the first level of decomposition, in that order. At the time a failure occurs, it is noted that IMFs display substantial disturbance components.

Fig.4. Configuration settings on at 40% of line length during LL failure (a) three phase voltages (b) Modal voltage Signal (c) intrinsic mode function-1

In Fig. 4 (c), we can see that the fault index was computed during the 0.03-second LL creation event. We find that the fault index is initially set to zero before any faults occur. And therefore, the suggested approach successfully detects LL faults in 0.03027 seconds. Therefore, the problem is identified within 0.27 milliseconds of the fault occurring.

iii. Double Line to Ground Fault

At 60% of the line length, with an inception angle of 90° and a fault resistance of 150Ω , a double line to ground (LLG) fault is modelled. The voltages recorded are decomposed to give the modal value of the output, which is further decomposed using VMD. At the first decomposition level, IMFs are acquired. At the first level of decomposition, IMFs are used to derive the proposed fault index. Fig. 5 (a), (b), and (c) show the three phase voltages, modal values, and IMF at the first level of decomposition, in that order. At the time a failure occurs, it is noted that IMFs display substantial disturbance components.

Fig.5. Configuration settings on at 60% of line length during LLG failure (a) three phase voltages (b) Modal voltage Signal (c) intrinsic mode function-1

As seen in Fig. 5 (c), the fault index was computed during the 0.025sec LLG fault occurrence. We find that the fault index is initially set to zero before any faults occur. As a result, the suggested approach successfully detects LLG faults in 0.02527 seconds. Consequently, the problem was recognized within 0.27 milliseconds of the fault occurrence.

iv. Line-Line-Line Fault

At 80% of the line length, with an inception angle of 30^0 (0.02166s) and a fault resistance of 100Ω , a LLL fault is modelled.

Fig.6. Configuration settings on at 80% of line length during LLL failure (a) three phase voltages (b) Modal voltage Signal (c) intrinsic mode function-1

The voltages recorded are decomposed to give the modal value of the output, which is further decomposed using VMD. At the first decomposition level, IMFs are acquired. At the first level of decomposition, IMFs are used to derive the proposed fault index. Fig. 6 (a), (b), and (c) show the three phase voltages, modal values, and IMF at the first level of decomposition, in that order. At the time a failure occurs, it is noted that IMFs display substantial disturbance components. As a result, the suggested approach successfully detects LLL faults in 0.02193 seconds. Consequently, the problem was recognized within 0.27 milliseconds of the fault occurrence.

v. *Line- Line-Line to Ground Fault*

At 50% of the line length, with an inception angle of 60° (0.0233s) and a fault resistance of 50Ω , a LLLG fault is modelled. Fig. 7 (a), (b), and (c) show the three phase voltages, modal values, and IMF at the first level of decomposition, in that order. At the time a failure occurs, it is noted that IMFs display substantial disturbance components. As a result, the suggested approach successfully detects LLLG faults in 0.0236 seconds. Consequently, the problem was recognized within 0.3 milliseconds of the fault occurrence.

Fig.6. Configuration settings on at 50% of line length during LLL failure (a) three phase voltages (b) Modal voltage Signal (c) intrinsic mode function-1

V. CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this research is to examine VMD fault detection in power systems. The suggested fault index is calculated by multiplying the corresponding values of the IMFs at the first decomposition stages. At each end of the transmission line, this fault index is computed. Faults LG, LL, LLG, LLL, and LLLG have been examined. In the absence of a defect, the fault indices are zero, but they take on non-zero values when an error occurs. Different kinds of errors can be distinguished from one another by obtaining threshold values. To categorize the different kinds of errors. There is no longer any need for zero sequence components according to the suggested approach. The results show that the suggested algorithm can successfully identify different kinds of power system failures. The approach is executed entirely inside the MAT LAB/SIMULINK framework.

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